

***In silico* study on the carbonic anhydrase activators : Activation of the human transmembrane isozyme XIV useful in Alzheimer's disease with amino acids and amines**

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Abstract : The quantitative structure activity relationships (QSAR) analysis on the activation of the human secretory isoform of the hCA XIV including a series of natural and non-natural amino acids and aromatic/heterocyclic amines are obtained. A heuristic algorithm is chosen as the best MLR equation in relation between the observed and the estimated values that is excellent ($Se = 0.3121$, $r^2 = 0.8759$, $F = 24.6933$, $r^2_{cv} = 0.7835$). The effort is to search the structural aspects of bioactive molecules.

Keywords : Carbonic anhydrase activation, PRECLAV, human membrane associated isoform (CA XIV).

Introduction

Mann and Keilin^{1,2} discovered carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) inhibition with sulfonamides and Leiner³⁻⁵, given details about its activation by different classes of compounds. An abundance of physiologically significant compounds such as amino acids, oligopeptides or small proteins, as well as lots of biogenic amines (histamine, serotonin and catecholamine's among others), were discovered to capably activate the catalytic activity of isoforms of the metalloenzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) which acts as an efficient catalyst for the inter conversion between carbon dioxide and bicarbonate at neutral pH⁶.

The earlier report⁷ that some CAAs (such as phenylalanine and imidazole) administered to experimental animals, could produce a significant pharmacological improvement of synaptic effectiveness, spatial learning, and memory proves that this class of comparatively unknown enzyme modulators may have pharmacological applications in conditions in which learning and memory are impaired, such as, for example Alzheimer's disease or aging⁵.

Supuran *et al.* reported an activation analysis of the

human carbonic anhydrase (hCA, EC 4.2.1.1) isozymes XIV applying a small library of natural/non-natural amino acids and aromatic/heterocyclic amines⁶⁻⁸. The important activation expression levels of CA XIV in the brain are helpful in developing pharmacologic agents for the management of chief disorders such as Alzheimer's disease⁸.

Material and methods :

(i) *Calibration set (experimental data)* :

Estimation, prediction and design of the activation constant ($\log K_A$) of hCA XIV (measured experimentally in the above mentioned study) have been discussed in this communication. A very important enzymatic activity shown by hCA XIV activator for the physiological reaction. Thus, observation of hCA XIV activation may be appropriate for a better understanding of hCA XIV, and for the prospective employ of modulators its activity for designing putative medicinal chemistry application¹⁻³. Supuran *et al.*⁸ observed that amino acids and amines of type **1-18** (Table 1) are active as CA XIV activators, with changeable efficacies, depending on their chemical structure.

The activation data of compounds are shown in Table 3 exhibiting a broad range of activation activity. The en-

Table 1. Structure of compounds **1-18** tested as CA XIV activators

L-His (Histidine) (1)		L-Phe (Phenylalanine) (3)
D-Phe (Phenylalanine) (4)		D-DOPA (Dihydroxyphenolalanine) (6)
L-DOPA (Dihydroxyphenolalanine) (5)		
L-Trp (Tryptophan) (7)		L-Tyr (Tyrosine) (9)
4-NH ₂ -L-Phe (Phenylalanine) (10)	Histamine (11)	Dopamine (12)
Serotonin (13)	2-Pyridyl-methylamine (14)	2-(2-Aminoethyl)pyridine (15)
	L-Adrenaline (18)	
1-(2-Aminoethyl)piperazine (16)	4-(2-Aminoethyl)morpholine (17)	

zyme activation data K_a values in the nanomolar (nM) were changed in 'A' according to the formula $A = \log/(1000/K_A)$ for CA activator XIV, and after, used as the dependent variable for QSAR study (Table 3). The activator activity (A) value of the molecules under the study spanned a broad range from 1 to 5. The choice of the test set is supposed to be such that it captures all the features and distinctiveness of the entire set of molecules. In this work, the CA XIV activators, i.e. the molecules with order **1**, **9**, **15** and **18** have composed the test set and the remaining as the training set and the molecules of the test set has captures all the features and span the activity range of the whole dataset. Thus, this study helps in design and synthesis of improved CA XIV activators. For

the validation of the preferred compound to the experimental and estimated activator activities of the compounds are summarized in Tables 4 and 5.

(ii) Prediction set (design of new compounds) :

The finding of new bioactive molecule is the most important mean of computational drug discovery. The compound **11** of calibration set was most potent hCA XIV activator. The prediction set contains 4 not yet synthesized new histamine derivatives of the analog of potent hCA XIV activator compound **11** shown in Table 2; generated by BROOD⁹ software having unknown observed values of CA XIV activator activity presented in Table 1 (compounds **19-22**).

Table 2. Structure of compounds **19-22** predicted as CA XIV activators*(iii) Descriptor calculation :*

The minimum energy geometry for each compound is performed by the conformational search capability of the Omega v.2.4.3^{10,11} program. Isomeric SMILES notation was used as program input in order to avoid any influences on conformational model generation by presenting 3D seed structures. Omega employs a rule-based algorithm^{10,11} in combination with variants of the Merck molecular force field 94. The force field used was the 94s variant of the MMMF_NoEstat (Merck Molecular force field)¹⁰⁻¹² which includes all MMFF terms except coulomb interactions. The conformations of minimum energy obtained by molecular mechanics calculations were further minimized by quantum chemical calculations. The semi empirical PM6 method¹³ included in the MOPAC 2009 software¹⁴ optimized the geometry more thoroughly.

The energy minimized structure is used to compute special molecular properties, as well as physicochemical, electronic, constitutional, virtual fragmentation descriptors, whole molecule quantum chemical (global) descriptors. MOPAC¹⁰⁻¹⁴ and PRECLAV¹⁵ programs are calculated over many descriptors for each molecule. The parameters to be computed are different descriptors that are investigative of molecular structure and used as independent variable. Recognition of the "significant" descriptors uses definite criteria¹⁶. The "significant" descriptors are those which are satisfactorily correlated with the dependent property. The variables having high enough diversity of values are measured as important only if their quality q is high enough.

$$q > 1 \quad (1)$$

where, $q = (1 - \min r^2) / (1 - r^2)$

(here $\min r^2 = 0.01$) and r^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the values of the analyzed descriptor and the values of the dependent property.

(iv) Chemometric tools :

The QSAR model built by dependent variables which is the experimental information related with biological activity. The parameters to be calculated are various descriptors that are indicative of molecular structure and used as independent variable. The PRECLAV algorithm^{15,16} was used for obtaining the parameters and for the statistical analysis as reported earlier¹⁷⁻²⁶.

The entire dataset has been used for the development of QSAR model with the help of stepwise multiple linear regression technique. PRECLAV computes thousand of QSAR equations i.e. multilinear formula, using only the significant descriptors^{15,16}.

The program combines successively sets with 2, 3, ..., k significant descriptors ($1 < k < 11$).

It is important to note that the descriptors which are of sufficiently low inter-correlated and fulfill criteria (2) may be possessed by such a set

$$r_{ij}^2 < N^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

where r_{ij}^2 = square of Pearson linear correlation between the values of two descriptors present in the same set and N = number of molecules in the calibration set (here $N = 18$).

Multilinear QSAR equation of type (3) is calculated by using each set of descriptors

$$A = C_0 + \sum C_k \cdot D_k \quad (3)$$

where A = a dependent property (here the inhibitory activity defined above), C_0 = intercept (free term), C_k = coefficients to the descriptors (weighting factors), D_k = significant descriptors and k = number of descriptors in the set.

The errors related to regression coefficients are not compute by the PRECLAV program.

The relative utility (U) of a certain descriptor was computed by the specified method¹⁵. The descriptors having a high value for [0-1000] are highly useful in estimating the activity because of their good correlation with activity. Thus each useful descriptor provides significant information about the variation of activity in different molecules to molecule.

Table 3. Value of the predictors used in QSAR study of calibration set and prediction set and CA XIV activator activities (in μM and $A = \log 1000/K_A$), estimated activities, Hat diagonal, standardized residual, $|RStudent|$ of the calibration set molecules **1-18** with predicted value (A) of the not yet synthesized ones **19-22**

Compd.	Obsd. K_a (μM)	A (Obsd.)	A (Estd.)	Residual	$ RStudent $	Hat diagonal	Compd.	A (predicted value)	Hat diagonal
1*	0.9	3.046	2.771	-0.275	0.8943	0.268	19	2.343	0.06
2	2.37	2.625	3.075	0.45	-1.4959	0.2219	20	8.477	15.3603
3	0.24	3.62	2.732	-0.888	3.7913	0.1264	21	-0.816	2.1377
4	7.21	2.142	2.043	-0.099	0.2892	0.1358	22	3.231	0.2782
5	12.1	1.917	1.696	-0.221	0.7684	0.3697			
6	36.8	1.434	1.854	0.42	-1.3908	0.2349			
7	16.5	1.782	1.934	0.152	-0.4534	0.1723			
8	18	1.745	1.538	-0.207	0.6256	0.1793			
9*	21.8	1.661	1.615	-0.046	0.1384	0.1848			
10	2.9	2.538	2.758	0.22	-0.7244	0.3037			
11	0.01	5	5.017	0.017	-0.0915	0.7312			
12	14.6	1.836	2.233	0.397	-1.3663	0.294			
13	6.5	2.187	2.015	-0.172	0.4848	0.0656			
14	21.7	1.664	1.678	0.014	-0.0463	0.3814			
15*	6.9	2.161	2.073	-0.088	0.3017	0.3779			
16	18.3	1.737	1.914	0.177	-0.6022	0.3588			
17	5.4	2.268	2.344	0.076	-0.2379	0.2584			
18*	36.1	1.442	1.518	0.076	-0.2534	0.3359			

Index with asterisk * molecules of test set.

(v) Quality of the model :

Usual statistical formulas are used to compute the 'quality' of each QSPR. Actually these formulas are a measure of agreement of observed/computed values of activity : standard error of estimation Se , Pearson square correlation r^2 , Fisher function F and cross-validated Pearson square correlation r_{cv}^2 . The concordance between the calculated/observed values has been calculated using the quality function Q^{16} which possesses values in the interval $\{-1, 1\}$.

$$Q = r^2 \cdot (N - k) / N \quad (4)$$

where r^2 = Pearson square linear correlation between computed/observed values and N = number of molecules in the calibration set (here $N = 18$).

By increasing the number of descriptors k , the quality Q of the equations increases, reaches a maximum, and then decreases. The equations with the highest Q was used for predictions and descriptors present in the equation are known as 'predictors'.

Leave one out (LOO) cross validation is the best method

to evaluate quality of regression model. In this method one biological activity value is divided into subsets (number of subsets = number of data points) of equal size. The cross-validated function r_{cv}^2 is a measure of homogeneity of calibration set from the point of view of predictors' set. We can say from the point of view of structure property relationships. The rank correlation Kendall¹⁶ is also used to validate the model.

As reported earlier^{27,28} PRECLAV divides the analyzed molecules into virtual fragments using an algorithm. The virtual fragments identified by PRECLAV do not always coincide with the classical functional groups. The presence or absence of significant fragments in the molecule predominantly affects the inhibitory activity of the molecule.

(vi) Applicability of domain and detection of outliers :

Predictive power of a model on the new data set is influenced by the similarity of chemical nature between calibration set and prediction set²⁹. A QSAR model can be used for screening new compounds if its domain of

Table 4. Observed, estimated and residual values of CA XIV activator activity (*A*) for the molecules used in the reduced calibration set (training set)

Compd.	Obsd. (<i>A</i>)	Estsd. (<i>A</i>)	Res.
2	2.625	2.986	-0.361
3	3.62	2.724	0.896
4	2.142	1.976	0.166
5	1.917	1.632	0.285
6	1.434	1.824	-0.39
7	1.782	1.93	-0.148
8	1.745	1.535	0.21
10	2.538	2.775	-0.237
11	5	4.954	0.046
12	1.836	2.216	-0.38
13	2.187	2.001	0.186
14	1.664	1.645	0.019
16	1.737	1.915	-0.178
17	2.268	2.38	-0.112

Table 5. Observed, estimated and residual values CA XIV activator activity (*A*) of compound used in the validation set (test set)

Comp.	Obsd. (<i>A</i>)	Estsd. (<i>A</i>)	Res.
1	3.046	2.662	0.387
9	1.662	1.553	0.109
15	2.161	2.153	0.008
18	1.443	1.5	-0.057

application is defined^{30,31} the need to typify the model applicability domain is also reflected in the OECD guidelines for QSAR model validation^{32,33}. QSAR model should only be used for making predictions of compounds that fall within the particular domain and considered reliable. One simple approach to define the applicability of the domain is extent of extrapolation³⁴⁻³⁶. This is based on the calculation of the Hat diagonal (leverage) h_i for each chemical, where the QSAR model is used to predict its activity³⁷.

$$h_i = \frac{1}{4} x_i^T (X^T X)^{-1} x_i \quad (6)$$

where x_i = the descriptor-row vector of the query molecule and $X = k \times n$ matrix containing the k descriptor values for each one of the n training molecules.

A Hat diagonal (leverage) value $> 3(k+1)/n$ (leverage warning limit³⁷ is considered large).

Outliers are observations that are poorly fit by the

regression model. Outlying compounds should not be removed unless a proper reason for their removal is present. The variance of the observed residuals is not constant which makes comparisons among them difficult. One of the solution to standardize the residuals^{38,39} is by dividing them by their standard deviations. This provides a set of residuals with constant variance. $|RStudent|$ (cross-validated Leave one out standardized residuals)³⁸ is a standardized residual that has the impact of a single observation removed from the mean square error. A molecule is defined as an outlier in which $|RStudent| > 2$ ³⁸. To visualize the applicability of domain of a developed QSAR model, William plot was used. In the William plot, $|RStudent|$ versus leverage values (h_i) are plotted. This plot could be used for a direct and simple graphical finding of both the response outliers and structurally important compounds in a model.

Results and discussion

Using the specific formulas and procedures of PRECLAV program algorithm, the statistical computations were conducted. Using only the "significant" descriptors PRECLAV computed ten thousand QSPR type (3) multilinear equations. The quality of the obtained equations can be reflected by the value of the Q function and also by values of some usual statistical functions. During the PRECLAV MLR analysis, we observed that the equation with highest value of the Q function is 4-parametric model and also that this model holds the highest predictive power which is as follows :

Dependent property : hCA activation activity CA XIV(A)

Molecules number in calibration set : 18

Number of "significant" descriptors in presence of prediction set = 242

$$A = 20.9763 + 1.9232 (D1) - 0.9894 (D2) - 52.3085 (D3) + 0.0016 (D4)$$

Whereas the quality of correlation is described by the statistical indices :

$$Se = 0.3121, r^2 = 0.8759, F = 24.6933, r_{cv}^2 = 0.7835, K = 0.7386$$

Se = standard error of values, r^2 = Pearson square correlation, F = Fisher function, r_{cv}^2 = Pearson cross-validated square correlation (Leave one out method), K =

Kendall rank correlation, $D1 = \mathbf{anc}$, (\mathbf{anc} : 100·Average atomic nucleophilic reaction index for C atoms); $D2 = \mathbf{sun}$, Molecular surface/number of atoms ratio $D3 = \mathbf{mzv}$, volume weighted dipole moment (Z component); $D4 = \mathbf{mob}$ (Moment of inertia B); $D1 \mathbf{anc}$: 100·Average atomic nucleophilic reaction index for C atoms ($U = 1000$).

The positive correlation of this predictor (\mathbf{anc}) shows that the activity increases with increase in this descriptor. $D2$ (\mathbf{sun}) Molecular surface/number of atoms ratio ($U = 988$). The negative correlation of $D2$ (\mathbf{sun}) predictor shows that the increase in the value of predictor causes the decrease to the activity. This was to confirm that the maximum value of this predictor is compounds **5-9** and found low activity of this entire compound. $D3$ (\mathbf{mzv}) predictor, volume weighted dipole moment (Z component) ($U = 806$); the negative correlation of this predictor indicates that increase in the value of \mathbf{mzv} predictor causes the decrease in the activity. $D4$ (\mathbf{mob}) Moment of inertia B ($U = 649$); the positive correlation of this descriptor shows the increasing the value of this descriptor increase the activity. The minimum correlation descriptor/activity is computed for $D4$ ($\mathbf{mob} = 0.0593$). The minimum intercorrelation between D_1/D_4 ($r^2 = 0.0029$) and the maximum intercorrelation between descriptors is computed for D_2/D_4 pair ($r^2 = 0.6384$). So the collinearity between the predictors are not found.

In this study, molecules of analyzed database include 18 virtual fragments but only one virtual fragment is considered significant. The percentages, in weight, of molecular fragments are well correlated (directly or inversely) with the values of inhibitory activity : $C_3H_3N_2$ (Imidazole) ($r = 0.7454$, Specimen compound **1**) play the dominant role for the activity. Because of the structure of the computed QSAR and the result of virtual fragmentation, I

think – the presence of substituted $C_3H_3N_2$ groups (compounds **1**, **2** and **11**) is favorable to activity. The removing the outliers out of calibration set in not recommended.

Average of the observed dependent property values = 2.267 ± 0.886

Average of the estimated dependent property values = 2.267 ± 0.829

External validation of the computation method :

In this work, the molecules with rank 1, 9, 15 and 18 for QSAR study constituted of the validation set and the remaining molecules formed the reduced calibration set. The validation set of 4 molecules (22% of the database) captured all the features and spanned the activity range of the entire data set. I may suppose that the reduced calibration set obtained in this method is a representative sample for the calibration set. The remaining 14 molecules formed the reduced calibration set. In the case when there is a validation set, the most important tool is the correlation between the estimated and experimental values of QSAR equation for the molecules in the validation set. In the presence of the validation set, we obtained the four parametric models for the reduced calibration set (for 14 molecules) with the predictors used in the above QSAR study and obtain results :

QSAR #1, $r^2 = 0.86761$, $F = 14.74491$, $Se = 0.1783$, $r^2_{pred} = 0.90767$

Hence, I can state that the estimated value for the molecules in the validation set are close to the experimental ones and have ordered the molecules in a series alike sufficient to the actual CA XIV activator value. This was confirmed by graph (Fig. 1) between observed and estimated value of calibration set and validation set. The predictive r^2 ($r^2_{pred} > 0.5$) parameter indicates significant ability of the developed model to predict the activation

Fig. 1. Graphs of observed vs estimated activity in the calibration set and validation set.

constant ($\log K_A$) of new compounds.

Applicability domain :

$|RStudent|$ of observed inhibitory activity and Hat diagonal (leverage) are used to assign applicability of domain (AD). Table 3 shows the values for leverage calculated for both calibration set and prediction set compounds. William plot (Fig. 2) shows the applicability of domain for the developed model of calibration set. The points with leverage value higher than the warning limit are the influential compounds except compound 3 for which the $|RStudent|$ is higher limit but Hat diagonal is with limit, therefore it is not considered as outlier. William plot, shows that all molecules is calibration set lie in the application domain of the developed model. Two mol-

Fig. 2. $|RStudent|$ of observed vs Hat diagonal.

ecules 20 and 21 have leverage value higher than warning leverage limit (0.666). Therefore the computed activity of the prediction set compounds 19 and 22 may be acceptable by using developed model of calibration set.

Conclusions

Statistically significant linear QSAR models imply the proposal of CA XIV activator for data representation, data modeling and data prediction. Polarity play dominant role for the activity and $C_3H_3N_2$ (imidazole) fragment is favorable for the CA XIV activator. Thus, attempts have been made to design and develop novel drugs against CA XIV activator activity on a rational basis so as to decreases the test and fault issue and predict the biological activity before synthesis.

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References

1. T. Mann and D. Keilin, *Nature*, 1981, **146**, 164.
2. A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 284.
3. M. Leiner and G. Leiner, *Biochemistry*, 1941, **311**, 119.
4. D. Vull, I. Nishimori, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 4303.
5. M. Şentürkn, H. Çavdar, O. Talaz and C. T. Supuran, "Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitors and Activators : Small Organic Molecules as Drugs and Prodrugs. Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, Medicinal Chemistry and Drug Design Book", ed. Deniz Ekinci, ISBN 978-953-51-0513-8, May 16, 2012.
6. J. Singh, B. Shaik, S. Singh, S. Sikhima, V. K. Agrawal, P. V. Khadikar and C. T. Supuran, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 6501.
7. M. K. Sun and D. L. Alkon, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 2001, **297**, 961.
8. D. Vullo, A. Innocenti, I. Nishimori, A. Scozzafava and C. T. Supuran, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2007, **17**, 4107.
9. BROOD (Version 2.0.0), OpenEye Science Software, 3600 Cerrillos Road, Suite 1107, Santa Fe, USA, 2010.
10. OMEGA (Version 2.4.3), OpenEye Science Software, 3600 Cerrillos Road, Suite 1107, Santa Fe, USA, 2010.
11. G. Tresadern, D. Bemporad and T. A. Howe, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2009, **27**, 860.
12. T. A. Halgr, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1999, **20**, 720.
13. J. J. P. Stewart, *J. Mol. Model*, 2007, **113**, 1173.
14. J. J. P. Stewart, MOPAC2012, Stewart Computational Chemistry, Colorado Springs, CO, USA, <http://OpenMOPAC.net>, 2012.
15. PRECLAV v.1011 (documentation included) is available from Center of Organic Chemistry – Bucharest, 2010.
16. L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2005, **56**, 639.
17. L. Tarko, C. E. Stecoza, C. Ilie and M. C. Chifiriuc, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2009, **60**, 476.
18. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2014, **29**, 877.
19. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2013, **21**, 1495.
20. S. Singh, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2015, **25**, 133.
21. S. Singh, *Med. Chem.*, 2012, **8**, 656.
22. S. Singh, *Lett. Drug Des. Discov.*, 2009, **6**, 286.
23. S. Singh and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2014, **29**, 449.
24. S. Singh, S. Singh and P. Shukla, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2011, **20**, 1556.
25. S. Singh, *Lett. Drug Des. Discov.*, 2011, **8**, 877.

26. S. Singh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A*, 2012, **82**, 113.
27. L. Tarko, *Rev. Chim. (Bucuresti)*, 2004, **55**, 539.
28. L. Tarko, *Arkivoc*, 2004, **xiv**, 74.
29. L. Eriksson, J. Jaworska, A. P. Worth, M. T. D. Cronin McDowell and R. M. P. Gramatica, *Environ. Health Perspect*, 2003, **111**, 1361.
30. A. Golbraikh and A. Tropsha, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2002, **20**, 269.
31. D. W. Osten, *J. Chemom.*, 1998, **2**, 39.
32. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development Guidance Document on the Validation of (Quantitative) Structure-Activity Relationship QSAR Models, OECD Document ENV/JM/MONO 2, 2007.
33. A. P. Worth, T. Aldenberg, I. Benjamin and M. T. D. Cronin, "Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships – The Report and Recommendations of ECVAM Workshop 52", ATLA, 2005, **33**, 155.
34. A. Tropsha, P. Gramatica and V. K. Gombar, *Comb. Sci.*, 2003, **22**, 69.
35. S. Weaver and M. P. Gleeson, *J. Mol. Graph Model*, 2008, **26**, 1315.
36. Georgia Melagraki, Antreas Afantitis Enalos KNIME nodes : Exploring corrosion inhibition of steel in acidic medium Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems 123, 2013.
37. L. Xu. Zhong, G. Yu. Ping, W. Bi. Zhao and A. H. Aisa Akber, *Structural Chemistry*, 2008, **19**, 959.
38. NCSS (Statistical Software Delux package), 329 North 1000 East, Kaysville, UT, USA, 2004.
39. Dennis R. Cook, "Residuals and Influence in Regression", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1982.